

Review on Periodic Acids and Periodates (Simple and Complex)

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THE oxy-acids of iodine in which the heptavalency of the element is manifested are called periodic acids and their corresponding salts periodates. The chemistry of periodates began when in 1833 Ammermuller and Magnue¹ discovered it in the oxidation of a mixture of iodine and sodium carbonate solution with chlorine. Till then so many works have been carried out in the preparation of newer compounds and investigation of their different properties. These compounds deserve speciality in that their properties etc. are different in many respects from the corresponding compounds of the other halogens, but resemble that of the tellurates. Greater size of the iodine atom is to some extent responsible to give these differences. The number of iodine(VII) compounds are also greater. Iodine is unique in that unlike the other halogens which are only tetraordinated, hexacoordination about iodine is the rule rather than the exception in periodates.

So far four review works have appeared in the literature to cover the chemistry of periodates and periodic acids. Amongst them Lister² and Jensovsky³ have discussed on the preparation, properties and some other studies of complex periodates of transition metals. The review of Siebert⁴ is exhaustive dealing much with the classification of periodates and investigating their structure and bondings. Dratovsky⁵ stresses much on the properties and thermal studies, while a systematic study will be found in standard work⁶.

The aim of the present work is to give an upto date information on the preparation, properties of periodic acid, periodates, periodato complexes along with their uses, bondings and structures.

Periodic acids are of several types. They may be thought to be derived from the union of different molecules of water with the I_2O_7 molecule. They are H_5IO_6 [para or ortho periodic acid or hexaoxiodic acid(VII)], HIO_4 [Metaperiodic acid, tetraoxiodic(VII) acid], H_3IO_5 [Mesoperiodic acid (hypothetical), pentaoxiodic acid], $H_4I_2O_6$ [diperiodic acid, enneaoxodiiodic(VII)], $H_6I_2O_{10}$ [decaoxodiiodic(VII) (hypothetical)], $H_8I_2O_{11}$ [Diparaperiodic acid, hendecaoxidiodic acid(VII) (hypothetical)], $H_{12}I_2O_{18}$ [Diorthoperiodic acid (hypothetical)] and $H_7I_3O_{14}$ [Triperiodic acid, (tetracaidecaoxotriiodic acid(VII))]. Literature also mentions $H_{11}I_3O_{18}$ and $H_{14}I_4O_{21}$. The older nomenclature is still most commonly used.

Dratovsky *et al.*⁵ have discussed on the preparation and properties of periodic acids and their salts. Here we shall discuss specially the investigation of newer ones. HIO_4 , $H_5I_2O_6$, $H_4I_2O_6$ and $H_7I_3O_{14}$ are solid. Although the hypothetical acids are still unknown, several salts of them have been prepared and studied well. $H_7I_3O_{14}$ is the latest addition to the acid series.

Orthoperiodic acid, H_5IO_6 :

Orthoperiodic acid is a weak acid ($pK_1 = 3.29$, $pK_2 = 8.3$, $pK_3 = 11.6$). According to Crouthamel *et al.*^{7,8} it is the only periodic acid that is stable in water. Recent study by Laser-Raman spectroscopy has confirmed⁹ the existence of a dimeric periodate in aqueous solution of 4-6M periodic acid. In aqueous solution ($pH = 0-7$) periodic acid exists as an equilibrium mixture between the free acid and its various ions and a shift in the equilibrium is expected on dilution or on mixing with an organic solvent¹⁰. Exchange of oxygen between periodate and water is very rapid^{11,12}. In strongly acid solutions it exists as $OI(OH)_5$. In very strongly acid media (10M $HClO_4$) protonated cation $[I(OH)_6]^+$ exists¹³, while in strong base, a dimeric species $[O_4I-O-I_4O_4]^{4-}$ is formed¹⁴.

The principal anions present in aqueous solutions of gradually increasing pH have been studied extensively by several author^{13,15-18}. The high lability of the I-O bond in the periodate ion IO_6^{5-} may be ascribed to the small, double-bond character of the octahedrally coordinated iodine^{9,12}. The iodic acid HIO_3 or in its ion, the bonds are mainly double bonds, thus reflecting the relative stability of the reagent.

Hydration of the metaperiodate ion

$$IO_4^- + 2 H_2O \rightleftharpoons H_4IO_6^-$$

is not catalysed by hydrogen ions, and is among the most rapid reactions of its kind. Although the mechanism may follow 1-step and 2-step paths, the latter one is more likely¹⁹. Solutions of periodic acid decomposes slowly into iodic acid and ozonised oxygen^{20,21}. Structural investigation confirms that it is genuine ortho acid $IO(OH)_5$ rather than $HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ or an oxonium salt $[H_5O_2]^+IO_4^-$ and resembles H_6TeO_6 . IR study also supports it. Nearly regular octahedral $IO(OH)_5$ molecules are linked by O-H-O bonds into a 3D array.

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Both $H_7I_5O_{14}$ and HIO_4 are extremely hygroscopic and are converted to H_5IO_6 with atmospheric moisture. H_5IO_6 reacts with H_2SO_4 and H_2SeO_4 to give²² $[I(OH)_6]HMO_4$ ($M = S, Se$). $H_4I_2O_9$ has been isolated in the solid state by the action of sulphuric acid on barium diperiodate or by the action of hydrochloric acid from its silver salt^{23,24}.

Salts of periodic acid :

Periodates can be divided into several classes :

Metaperiodates : IO_4^-
 Mesoperiodates : IO_5^{3-} or HIO_5^{2-}
 Orthoperiodates : IO_6^{5-} , $H_2IO_6^{4-}$, $H_3IO_6^{3-}$,
 $H_4IO_6^{2-}$
 Diperiodates : $I_2O_9^{4-}$, $I_2O_{10}^{6-}$, $I_2O_{11}^{8-}$,
 $I_2O_{12}^{10-}$, $HI_2O_{10}^{5-}$,
 $H_2I_2O_{10}^{4-}$, $H_3I_2O_{10}^{3-}$
 Triperiodates : $H_2I_3O_{14}^{5-}$, $H_4I_3O_{14}^{3-}$

Information of different simple metal periodates are given in the literature^{18,25-39}.

Periodate oxidises As(III), Sb(III), Sn(II), Te(IV), Cr(III) and Mn(II) ions under different conditions and especially at higher temperatures to yield their highest oxidation states. Oxidation and subsequent precipitation of metal periodates occur in the case of Fe(II), Ti(I), Hg(I) and Ce(III) at higher temperatures. Precipitation of metal periodates occur with almost all the heavy ions, except Pt(IV), Al(III), Au(III), U(VI), V(V), W(VI), Mo(VI) and Ge(IV). Most of the heavy metal periodates are formed in neutral or slightly acidic media and are soluble in dilute acid. The Pb(II), Tl(III), Pd(II) and Be(II) salts are formed in strongly basic solution. Barium and potassium salts are the only ones which precipitate from the alkaline earth and alkali metal groups⁴⁰.

Systematic studies of Gr-III periodates have been performed⁴¹⁻⁴⁹. The general formula given is $MH_2IO_6 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Sc, Y, La-Lu$) except cerium for which the formula is $CeHIO_6 \cdot nH_2O$. Infrared spectra indicate their similarity of structure. Extensive work on rare earth periodates has been carried out by Lokio *et al.* They have shown that Ce(IV) is the most soluble of the lanthanoids known for their poor solubility⁴⁰. $Pr(I_2O_9)_3 \cdot 24H_2O$ is also known^{4,51}. By solid state reaction $M^I_2IO_6$ and $M^I_2IO_6$ can be prepared^{52,53}. A penta-coordinated periodate species has recently been detected⁵⁴.

Mixed metal paraperiodates of the type $M^I M^{IV} IO_6$ ($M^I = Na, K, NH_4, Rb, Cs$ and $M^{IV} = Ni, Mn, Pb, Ge, Sn$) have been prepared⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸. They may belong to the complex variety. Those of Germanium and tin can be prepared by adding $M^{IV}Cl_4$ and $M^I NO_3$ to H_5IO_6 and aging the precipitate. Recently the present authors have prepared mixed metal periodates of cerium (IV) e.g. $M^I CeIO_6 \cdot xH_2O$ ($M^I = Li, Na$, from alkaline solution. All these compounds are insoluble in water and alkali.

Literature surveys the results of Mass spectrum⁵⁹, Mössbauer spectra⁶⁰, Force constants^{46,61,62}, ionic mobility⁶ and some thermodynamic parameters⁶.

Periodato compounds having metal ion in an unusually high valence state :

These compounds contain an anionic complex containing mainly transition metal atom of higher valency as central atom and periodate anions as ligands. The behaviour of periodate ions lies in the oxidation of the metal ion to a higher valent state and its subsequent stabilisation. However, in some cases, still stronger oxidising agents are required and periodate then acts as a stabilising agent for these higher valencies. Common oxidising agents are sodium or potassium persulphate or hypochlorite and electrolytic oxidation. In most instances alkali salts of the following hypothetical acids and in a very few cases the acids themselves have been prepared e.g. $H_{11}Mn(IO_6)_8$ ^{63,64}, $H_2Mn_2I_2O_{11}$ ⁶⁵, $HMnIO_6$ ⁶⁶, H_2FeIO_6 ⁶⁷⁻⁷¹, $H_7Fe(IO_6)_2$ ⁷², $H_3Fe_4(IO_6)_8$ ⁷², $H_7Co_9(IO_6)_2$ ^{64,73,74}, $H_3Co_4(IO_6)_8$ ⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷, $HNiIO_6$ ^{78,79}, $H_7Cu(IO_6)_2$ ^{75,80-83}, $H_7Ag(IO_6)_2$ ^{75,83-86}, $H_7Au(IO_6)_2$ ⁶⁷, $H_6Ce(IO_6)_2$ ⁸⁷, $H_3UO_2IO_6$ ⁸⁸, $H_6Ru(IO_6)_2(OH)_2$ ^{89,90}, $H_2R_2O_5(IO_6)_2$ ⁹¹ ($R = Nb, Ta$), $[I(MO_4)_6]^{5-}$ ^{92,93}, $[IO_5(MO_4)]^{6-}$ [where $M = Mo(VI), W(VI)$], $[JO_2(MO_4)_4]^{6-}$ [where $M = Mo(VI)$]⁶, $H_2[M'(IO_4)_6]^{94}$ [where $M' = La^{+3}, Pr^{+3}, Er^{+3}$], $H_2[M'(IO_4)_6]^{94}$ where $M' = Ce^{+4}, Th^{+4}$. The metal ions are Mn(IV), Fe(III), Co(III), Ni(IV), Cu(III), Ag(III), Au(III), Ce(IV), Ru(VI), Nb(V), Ta(V), Mo(VI), W(VI). Some other complexes of V(V)⁹⁵, Bi(III)⁹⁶, Nb⁹⁷, Ru(IV), Pt(IV) and Pd(IV)⁸⁹ have been described. Previously mentioned $MCeIO_6 \cdot xH_2O$ may belong to complex variety⁹⁸. Hitherto unknown soluble complex periodates of gallium and nickel have also been claimed⁹⁹. The complexes of V, Nb and Ta are more stable in acid medium.

Complex cations only with smaller (e.g. Co^{+2}) ionic potential give difficultly soluble compounds¹⁰⁰ with $H_7Cu(IO_6)_2$ or $H_7Ag(IO_6)_2$. Periodates with a complex cation, the central atom of which is an atom of metal with a strong complex forming ability, e.g. $Co(III)$ ¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰³, $Cr(III)$ ¹⁰⁴, $Pd(II)$, $Pt(II)$, $Pt(IV)$ ¹⁰⁵ are well known. Periodate anions do not usually enter the coordination sphere of these compounds. The heteropolyanions in which the iodine-metal ratio is 1:6, have received comparatively little attention.

Complex rare-earth and actinide periodates are prepared from the alkali solution. The compounds are usually coloured and moderately soluble in water. The salts with many Na/K atoms are moderately less soluble in water. The higher valencies of the central metal atoms have been demonstrated by titration with a suitable reductant or by measuring the magnetic susceptibility. Information on the type of bonding and the configuration of the central atom have been obtained from the diamagnetic behaviour of Cu(III), Ag(III), Co(III) and

Ni(IV) and the paramagnetic behaviour of Fe(III) and Mn(IV) complexes. Slight paramagnetism of NaNiO_6 , KNiO_6 or $\cdot\text{H}_2\text{Co}_4\text{I}_8\text{O}_{24}\cdot\text{H}_{12}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been attributed to some type of dissociation or the presence of lower valent metals. The cobalt complex acid has shown some semi-conducting property¹⁰⁶. The low magnetic moment value for the Fe(III) complexes has been attributed to the presence of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$, different forms of ferric oxide and oxygen bridges between iron atoms⁷². Oxobridging has also been suggested in the ruthenium complex. Planar stereochemistry with dsp^2 hybridisation is present with the d^8 system e.g. Cu(II), Ag(III) and Au(III). Periodate ion acts as a bidentate ligand in these cases coordinating through filled bonding orbitals of oxygen atoms. Octahedral configuration has been suggested for the Mn(IV), Co(III), Ni(IV) and Fe(III) complexes and also for iodine in these complexes. The influence of the metals on the electronic configuration of the complexes have been discussed⁸⁹. Only Co(III) and Fe(III) give condensed heteropolyacid by acidification of their soluble salt. The hexol-like chiral configuration based on the Anderson model has been suggested¹⁰⁷ for the former acid. Diastereoisomers of this acid derivative have been separated. The above structure being substantiated by the present authors. The anionic species for the Ag(III) and Cu(III) complexes¹⁰⁸ is $[\text{M}(\text{HIO}_6)_2]^{5-}$.

The complex periodates are more stable in alkaline medium but some of them retain their stability in acid e.g. $\text{H}_7\text{Co}(\text{IO}_6)_2$, $\text{H}_{11}\text{Mn}(\text{IO}_6)_3$ and $\text{H}_2\text{UO}_2\text{IO}_6$ and can be obtained by passing a solution of their soluble salts through a suitable cation exchange resin. The simpler Mn(IV) salts, however, show no tendency to decompose in water as the complex salts containing more periodate do. The ruthenium salt decomposes to RuO_4^{2-} ion in dilute basic solution. Cu(III), Co(III) and Mn(IV) complexes show high formation constants.

Like the simple periodates, the complex anion often contain protons, attached to I-O bonds, which ionise only with great difficulty if at all. $\text{H}_7\text{Co}(\text{IO}_6)_2$ and $\text{H}_{11}\text{Mn}(\text{IO}_6)_3$ show five and seven protons respectively. The coloured complexes show absorption bands both in u.v. and visible region. The bands in the u.v. and the first band in the visible region with high extinction coefficient are charge-transfer bands and the others originate from d-d transitions^{80, 89, 108, 109}. Hauck¹¹⁰ from his studies on lithium orthoperiodate has concluded that periodates give two strong bands due to $T_{1u}(\sigma) \rightarrow A_{1g}^*(\sigma)$, and $E_g(\sigma) \rightarrow A_{1g}^*(\sigma)$ or $A_{1g}(\sigma) \rightarrow A_{1g}^*(\sigma)$ transition, and a weak band at 24000cm^{-1} due to $T_{2u}(\pi) \rightarrow A_{1g}^*(\sigma)$ or $\pi \rightarrow A_{1g}^*(\sigma)$ transition.

Thermal Study :

Dratovsky⁸ in his work has dealt with much on the thermal properties of different periodates. A survey, however, will reveal that the thermal behaviour of many periodates is either misunderstood or

unexplored. However quite definite results have been obtained with simpler salts. These reveal that the thermal decomposition of periodates of various stoichiometries is accompanied by loss of water, oxygen and iodine. Reactions include partial¹¹¹ or complete dehydration^{38, 112} formation of iodate¹¹³, iodine (VI)¹¹⁴, iodide¹¹⁵, oxide¹¹⁶ or the metal itself (for heavy metals). The behaviour of silver-periodates at higher temperatures differ from those of analogous lithium and sodium periodates. This phenomenon is attributed to a catalytic effect of the metallic silver¹¹⁷. Between 500°C the decomposed products are mixtures of Ag_2IO_6 and AgIO_3 , Ag_2IO_6 and AgIO_3 , AgIO_3 and Ag_2O and $\text{AgI} + \text{Ag}\cdot\text{NH}_4\text{IO}_4$ decomposes to NH_3 and HIO_4 at 156-180°C and explodes at 192°C¹¹⁸. Salts of some condensed acids can be obtained starting with simpler ones in the thermal decomposition processes^{47, 112, 113, 119, 120}.

Lokio and Kyrki⁴⁷ have carried out an exhaustive work on the thermal decomposition of Lanthanoid hexaoxiodates (VII), $\text{LnH}_2\text{IO}_6\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{Ln} = \text{Nd} - \text{Lu}$). End product is always oxide. Activation energies and order of reactions for the decompositions have also been calculated. The non-isothermal kinetics for the decomposition reaction have been investigated¹²¹. Implication of pseudo first order decomposition of the metal iodates is that chemical decomposition determines the rate¹²². Sanyal and Nag¹¹³ have calculated different thermodynamic parameters for their reactions :

Thermolysis of $\text{M}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M = Ca, Sr, Ba) gives intermediate MIO_4 which decompose with increasing temperature to $\text{M}_2(\text{IO}_6)_2$ probably via $\text{M}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ and finally to the metallic oxides. The stability order of the ortho-periodates being $\text{Ba} > \text{Sr} > \text{Ca}$.

Dratovsky has discovered that many dimesoperiodates on heating form intermediate products in which the formal oxidation state of iodine is +6 e.g. $\text{CaIO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ¹²⁴, $\text{MgIO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ¹²⁵, PbIO_4 ¹²⁶. It has been reported that these compounds are stable in dry air but disproportionate to their iodates and periodates in contact with water⁵

Sanyal and Nag¹¹³ have, however, claimed the following hydrolytic reaction to take place :

MIO_4 compounds do not contain any peroxo linkage. Infrared spectra showed the absence of water in MIO_4 which disagrees with the formulation of $\text{MIO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ by Dratovsky.

Julak¹¹⁴, during his studies on the thermal decomposition of Gr IIA metals, have noticed paramagnetism associated with the intermediate products formed at 110-250° resulting from adsorbed molecular oxygen. From the magnetic susceptibility dependence on temperature, the strength of the oxygen adsorption was found to increase in the series Mg < Ba < Be < Ca.

Mixed metal periodates of the type $M\text{SnIO}_6$ ($M = \text{Na, K, Rb, Cs, NH}_4$) decomposes according to⁵⁸

Although there is no mention of the thermal decomposition of complex periodates in the literature, the present authors have studied some of them^{106, 127} e.g.

Thermodynamic parameters have, sometimes, been calculated. Thermal studies of the complex periodates of gallium and nickel and of some complex tellurates are being carried out⁹⁹.

Structure :

The structure of periodates has been investigated by X-ray diffraction method, Infrared, Raman, electronic, NMR and Mossbauer spectral analysis, by neutron diffraction and in few instances by NQR, optical second harmonic generation (SHG) technique and magnetic susceptibility measurements. X-ray diffraction method is by far the best. Most of the anhydrous periodates are tetragonal. They are isostructural with Scheelite and their anions form tetrahedra e.g. IO_4^- in NaIO_4 is a slightly compressed tetrahedron having two bond angles of 114° and four of 107°, whereas in the structure of orthoperiodates the IO_6^{5-} anions are arranged in octahedra. The iodine atom is invariably surrounded by an octahedron of oxygens, but the coordination of the metal atom is determined by the crystal field and other demands peculiar to its oxidation state. The

iodine and metal atoms in these compounds are linked via I-O-M bridges. The diperiodate anions are made up of two octahedra sharing an edge or a face. The simple octahedral IO_6^{5-} ion occurs in anhydrous salts $M_5\text{IO}_6$ whereas distorted IO_6 structure in $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ has been observed. In KNiO_6 , however, K, Ni and I all occupy octahedral positions in a nearly hexagonal closest packing of O atoms¹²⁸. Some incorrectly interpreted structures has been corrected e.g. the structures of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$, $[\text{Mg}(\text{OH}_2)_6]_2$, $[\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{10}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}_2\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{10} \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. X-ray reveals the presence of octahedral $\text{IO}_3(\text{OH})_3^{2-}$ ion in these compounds¹²⁹. The actual structure of cadmium and magnesium salts being $\text{Cd}[\text{O}_3\text{I}(\text{OH})_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Mg}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{2+}[\text{O}_3\text{I}(\text{OH})_3]^{2-}$. Even the trigonal crystal $\text{NaIO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been shown to be octahedral¹³⁰ and formulated as $\text{NaH}_3\text{O}[\text{O}_3\text{I}(\text{OH})_3]$. In NaIO_4 each Na^+ ion is surrounded by 8 oxygen atoms¹³¹ at distances of 2.54 or 2.60 Å. The hexagonal $M\text{SnIO}_6$ compounds are isomorphous⁵⁷ with MPbIO_6 . NH_4IO_4 is anomalous among the Scheelite periodates¹³². In $\text{LnIO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^{133,134} ($\text{Ln} = \text{Pr-Lu, Y}$) octahedral $\text{IO}_4(\text{OH})_2$ is bound via the LnO_6 polyhedrons e.g. in samarium¹³⁴, the structure consists of chains formed by $\text{IO}_4(\text{OH})_2$ octahedron and 8 coordinate $\text{SmO}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ groups. The copper complex periodate, $\text{Na}_3\text{KH}_3\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been found to possess a squareplanar configuration with the plane formed by one edge from each of the two periodate octahedra, and with one water molecule at a distance of 2.70 Å from the copper atom¹³⁵. The silver complex is supposed to have the same structure⁸⁰.

Structures of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{CIA}](\text{IO}_4)_2$ ($A =$ pyridine etc.) and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}]\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($X =$ uninegative ion) have also been investigated^{136,137}. A review on spatial structures of periodates with an unfilled co-ordination environment has recently been published¹³⁸.

Infrared and Raman spectroscopy have served immensely for the characterisation of different periodate species and in some cases for the elucidation of their structures. Siebert¹³⁹ has shown from Raman spectroscopy that the 'I' atoms are octahedrally coordinated by 'O' atoms in both HIO_4 and $\text{H}_7\text{I}_3\text{O}_{14}$ implying a polymeric structure for HIO_4 . The structure of the condensed acid has been suggested to be

The central -OH groups are trans to each other. Raman spectra have shown that the iodine co-ordination in $\text{NaIO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is not tetrahedral but is octahedral¹³⁰ i.e. $\text{NaH}_3\text{O}[\text{IO}_3(\text{OH})_3]$. In the compounds MM^IIO_6 ($M = \text{Na, K, Rb, Cs, NH}_4$; $M^I = \text{Ge, Sn, Pb}$) the influence of M and M^I on the IR

and Raman frequency has been investigated¹⁴⁰. Presence of IO_6 and $\text{M}^{\text{I}}\text{O}_6$ octahedra as the structural unit has been suggested. The octahedral structure for the IO_6^{5-} ion in H_5IO_6 or its salts has been confirmed¹⁴⁰. Literature surveys some more informations on Raman Spectroscopy^{17,141-143}. The tetrahedral structure of IO_4^- ion in NaIO_4 etc. has been confirmed by Infrared study¹⁴⁴ which also lends support¹⁴⁵ to the presence of LiO_4 tetrahedra and IO_6 octahedra in $\text{LiIO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Although IO_4^- is present in $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \cdot (\text{IO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LiIO}_4 \cdot \frac{2}{3}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ presence of H_4IO_6^- ion has been confirmed¹⁴¹ in $\text{LiIO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Al}(\text{IO}_4)_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \cdot (\text{IO}_4)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and is formulated as $\text{LiH}_4\text{IO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](\text{H}_4\text{IO}_6)_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \cdot [\text{H}_4\text{IO}_6]_3$. The influence of cation radii on the crystal symmetry, force constants and vibrational frequencies has been discussed¹⁴¹. Correct formulation has sometimes been possible with the help of IR study¹⁴². Rare-earth periodates has been formulated¹⁴⁶ as $\text{LnH}_2\text{IO}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, lanthanum as $\text{LaIO}_5 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, germanium periodate¹⁴⁷ as $\text{Ge}(\text{OH})\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Anhydrous alkaline-earth metaperiodates contain tetrahedral anion but the hydrated salts contain ortho-periodate anion¹⁴⁸. Relation of symmetry and vibrational frequencies has been discussed¹⁴⁹. The present authors have carried out infrared studies on some complex periodates^{98,99}.

The information obtained from infrared spectra of different periodates are tabulated below^{4,6,7,64,141,150-153}.

TABLE-1 INFRARED INFORMATION OF PERIODATES

Frequencies (cm^{-1})	Character of vibration
3100-3400	O-H stretching, weakly hydrogen-bonded
2200-2900	O-H stretching, strongly hydrogen-bonded
2350-2380	I-OH deformation (overtone)
1600, 3400	water of crystallisation
1070-1310	I-OH deformation
840-950	I-OH torsion (found only with strong hydrogen bonds)
600-850	I-O stretching
790-850	I-O " (in IO_4^-)
500-600	I-O-I "
400-440	I-O-I deformation
250-550	O-I-O deformation

Neutron diffraction experiment¹⁵⁴ has been applied to study the structures of antiferroelectric $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}_5\text{IO}_6$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_5\text{IO}_6$; NMR technique¹⁵⁵ for the structure of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}_5\text{IO}_6$, NQR¹⁵⁶ for NH_4IO_4 , electronic spectra for the structure of some complex periodates^{64,7,63,99,109,157} and optical second harmonic generation (SHG) technique¹⁵⁸ for sodium periodate.

The structure of periodates has also been investigated on the basis of magnetic susceptibility

measurements¹⁵⁹. The results of these measurements have sometimes enabled complexes to be distinguished from simple compounds^{30,47,160}.

Bonding :

The ion IO_4^- is formed through $d\pi-p\pi$ bonding to oxygen superimposed on the molecular frame work of σ -bonds. The iodine atom is assumed to use its s and p orbitals for σ -bonding. After electrons have been allotted to the inner shells, to four tetrahedral sp^3 σ -bonds, and to four σ -lone pairs at the back of each oxygen atom, there remains sixteen electrons needing eight molecular orbitals. These orbitals may be built up from the $2p\pi$ and $2p\pi$ -orbitals on each oxygen and the five d-orbitals of the I-atom. There are two strongly π -bonding molecular orbitals with the E-symmetry (using $d_{xy}2, d_{z^2}$ orbitals), three weakly π -bonding molecular orbitals with T_2 Symmetry (using d_{xy}, d_{yz} and d_{zx} orbitals) and three non-bonding combinations of oxygen orbitals in T_1 . Thus giving the eight desired orbitals¹⁶¹. d_{z^2} and $d_{xy}2$ orbitals are particularly well suited for this overlapping and have about $\sqrt{5}$ times as much overlap with the $p\pi$ -orbitals as one of the other three d-orbitals.

In the octahedral structure of IO_6^{5-} ion, the central atom uses sp^3d^2 hybridisation. It may be assumed that one of the oxygen atoms is held by a coordinate link and the other five O^- ions by shared pair covalent bonds. Alternatively, one may assume a valence shell of $7+5=12$ electrons around iodine. Each sp^3d^2 hybrid then carries one pair which makes coordinate bonds to the six oxygen atoms.

Kinetics and Mechanism :

Some kinetic studies on the the mechanism of periodate oxidations have been discussed¹⁶² and others are still under active investigation. Thermodynamic parameters, have, sometimes been furnished. From their observations various types of mechanisms have been suggested. The reaction rates have been found to be functions of pH and complex ion concentrations. In case of periodic acid oxidation the acid itself and in some cases its anions take part in the reaction.

The first of itis kind to be studied was the decomposition of $\text{Na}_7\text{H}_4\text{Mn}(\text{IO}_6)_3$ to MnO_4^- , IO_3^- and OH^- ions^{63,64}. An inner-sphere mechanism involving pseudo first order reaction rate has been suggested in the oxidation of VO_2^{2+} ion^{163,164} and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ ion¹⁶⁵, whereas in the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ oxidation, formation of free radicals has been ascertained¹⁶⁶. An associative-type mechanism common to other square-planar low-spin d^8 ions has been suggested for the ligand exchange reaction of $\text{Ag}(\text{III})$ complexation¹⁶⁷. Other oxidation include of tartaric acid¹⁶⁸ and alcohol¹⁶⁹ by diperiodatocuprate, hexacyanoferrate by IO_4^- in the presence of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ catalysis¹⁷⁰, $\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})^{2-}$ by IO_4^- ion¹⁷⁰, phosphine

to orthophosphoric acid in the presence of W catalyst¹⁷¹, iodide to iodine in the presence and absence of Ir(IV) catalyst¹⁷², ruthenate¹⁷³ by IO_4^- , potassium hexachloroiridate(III) with periodic acid¹⁷⁴, the oxidation¹⁷⁵ of $[\text{M}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{NCS}]^{2+}$ where $\text{M} = \text{Cr}^{+3}$ and Co^{+3} , and the thermal decomposition of NH_4IO_4 ¹¹⁸. Studies on the catalytic activity of H^+ and OH^- ions in the oxidation of phosphite by H_5IO_6 ¹⁷⁶ and of Cr(III) and Os(VIII) on the periodate-arsenite reaction have been made¹⁷⁷. Mechanism of formation^{183, 184} of $[\text{IMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{5-}$ from MoO_4^{2-} and H_5IO_6 ^{92, 178} and the formation and decomposition of Cu(III) periodate complex in alkaline solutions has also been studied¹⁷⁹.

Uses :

Periodic acid and periodates are known for their oxidising property and hence their uses are manifold. Their oxidising property is a function of pH. In acid solution, it is one of the most powerful oxidising agents known ($E^0 \text{IO}_4^-/\text{IO}_3^- = 1.60\text{V}$) while in alkaline solution, it is slightly less oxidising than hypochlorite¹⁸⁰ ($E^0 = 0.70\text{V}$). The oxidising power of free HIO_3 is slightly lower than that of periodic acid. In strongly acid medium, they oxidize iodide exclusively to iodine, whereas in neutral solution as in the presence of NaHCO_3 , iodide ion reduces periodates to iodates.

The liberated iodine is then titrated with a standard solution of sodium arsenite^{181, 182}, or with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. Alternatively, the iodate concentration, as in the latter one, may be determined polarographically¹⁸³ or spectrophotometrically¹⁸⁴. It is better to carry out a blank titration side by side. For slow reactions periodate solution should be kept in the dark as periodate solutions slowly form ozone in daylight^{185, 186}. The various iodometric titrations have been described in the literature^{186, 187}.

The limited solubility of the commonly used periodates, their high molecular weight and the frequent appearance of iodine are the principal drawbacks to their preparative use.

Periodate can be detected by the formation of greenish-yellow precipitate with AgNO_3 solution, by yellow colour¹⁸⁸ with Manganese—2 : 2'-bipyridine and isobutylmethyl ketone at pH 4-9, by the formation of violet colour on paper with Al(III)-morin reagent solution¹⁸⁹, by adding MnO_2 to HIO_4 , warming the solution and adding one drop of 6N HNO_3 to give a pale-red solution¹⁹⁰ or by using thiourea, o-phenylenediamine or Na_2SO_3 reagent¹⁹¹.

Periodate can be estimated spectrophotometri-

cally directly at 222.5 nm¹⁹² or in more concentrated solution at 260 nm¹⁹³. Other spectrophotometric methods are also known¹⁹⁴⁻¹⁹⁶. It can also be estimated gravimetrically¹⁹⁷, polarographically¹⁹⁸, potentiometrically¹⁹⁹, colorimetrically²⁰⁰, by enthalpimetric titration²⁰¹, volumetrically²⁰² by $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ and by radio crystallography²⁰³. Periodates can be separated by ion-exchange resin and paper chromatography²⁰⁴. Periodic acid and periodates have been used extensively as an oxidising agent in organic chemistry specifically for the cleavage of 1,2 diols and related compounds from Malaprade's time²⁰⁵. It has now become an indispensable tool for the structure determination of natural products and more recently, the nucleic acids.

The applications, including some mechanisms of periodic acid and periodates to different fields of organic and bioorganic chemistry have been extensively reviewed by Sklarz²⁰⁶ and more recently by Fatiadi²⁰⁷.

Simple as well as complex periodates have, of late, found qualitative and quantitative applications in chemistry. In the qualitative field periodates have been used for the detection of lithium²⁰⁸, ferrocene derivatives on paper chromatogram²⁰⁹, vanadium²¹⁰ (IV & V), silver, tin and manganese^{211, 212}, carbohydrates in paper chromatography²¹³.

In analytical chemistry in the determination of ruthenium^{214, 215}, rhodium²¹⁶ and manganese²¹⁷ spectrophotometrically, in the gravimetric determination of praseodymium²¹⁸ as PrH_2IO_6 , lithium²²⁹ as Li_2IO_6 , silver²²⁰ as $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$, ytterbium^{221, 222} as $\text{YbH}_2\text{IO}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Yb}_2(\text{IO}_6)_3$, indium²²³ as $\text{In}_2(\text{IO}_6)_3$, thallium²²⁴ as $\text{Tl}_2(\text{IO}_6)_3$, cerium as $\text{CeHIO}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^{121, 222, 225-227}, thorium²²⁸ as Chromium²²⁸⁻²²⁹ $\text{Th}_5(\text{IO}_6)_4$ and copper as Cu_2HIO_6 ²²⁹.

It is more suitable for the oxidimetric determination of vanadium (IV) than many of the usually preferred oxidants—the advantage being the speed, accuracy and stability of periodate solution¹⁸³. Many periodate oxidations are also susceptible to trace metal catalysis and these are useful for the determination of very small amounts of catalysts such as Ruthenium^{214, 230, 231}, Rhodium^{216, 232}, Chromium²²⁸⁻²²⁹ Manganese²³³⁻²³⁵, Osmium²³⁴ and Iridium²³⁹.

Some other determinations include Manganese²¹², Copper²⁴⁰, Nickel²⁴¹, Mercury²⁴², Lanthanum, Barium and Indium by photochemical reduction²⁴³, hydrogen peroxide²⁴⁴, mercaptans^{245, 246}, vitamin C²⁴⁷, ferrocyanide²³⁸, S^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , HSO_3^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ alone or in mixtures²⁴⁹, mixture containing S^{2-} , HS^- , SO_3^{2-} , HSO_3^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, trithionates and tetrathionates²⁵⁰, mixture of Br^- , hypophosphite, phosphite, As(III), Se(IV) and Te(IV)²⁵¹. Determination has also been performed in oxidised mixtures by spot tests²⁵². Other uses are as corrosion inhibitor^{253, 254} in dye industry²⁵⁵, in the quantitative and rapid separation of Th from U(VI) etc. through

a bed of bismuth or lead periodate²⁵⁶. The periodate/Schiff reagent was first applied for histochemical, animal-tissue analysis (known as the McManus-Lillie test²⁵⁷ to the detection of carbohydrates²⁵⁸ and in structural analysis²⁵⁹.

Complex copper(III) and silver(III) periodates have received attention as an analytical tool in the domain of complex periodates. Diperioato cuprate(III) has been used in the estimation of formic acid, oxalic acid and acetic acid mixtures²⁶⁰, carboxylic acid mixtures²⁶¹, calcium and magnesium²⁶², hexoses and sucrose^{265,266} hexacyanoferrates, arsenite and thiosulphate²⁶⁴, sugars^{265, 266}, alcohols, aldehydes and ketones²⁶⁷, Neptunium(VI) and Plutonium(VI)²⁶⁸ and to oxidise some triazene compounds²⁶⁹. Periodates of Ag, Cu, Fe, Co, Ni etc. have been utilised as the anode in a battery prepared with organic electrolytes²⁷⁰. Some more applications of Ag(III) and Cu(III) complexes have been studied²⁷¹⁻²⁷⁵. The oxidation potential of $K_7Cu(IO_6)_2$ in alkaline medium has been found²⁷⁶ to be +0.80V. $Na_6Ru(IO_6)_2(OH)_2 \cdot xH_2O$ has been suggested as a very good source of ruthenium tetroxide for use in organic and inorganic syntheses⁹⁰.

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CHAUDHURY & MUKHERJEE : REVIEW ON PERIODIC ACIDS AND PERIODATES ETC.

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